

DRL for Joint Active and Passive Beamforming in RIS-aided MIMO Systems

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Abstract

Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RISs) are an emerging technology that enhances communication spectral efficiency (SE) by using an array of controllable, low-cost, and energy-efficient elements to dynamically manipulate the wireless channel. However, achieving these gains requires the joint optimization of the active transmit beamforming at the base station and the passive phase shifts at the RIS. Conventional iterative optimization algorithms, while effective, suffer from high computational complexity and latency due to slow convergence, especially for multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) systems with a large number of RIS elements. To overcome these limitations, in this paper, we leverage proximal policy optimization (PPO), a robust deep reinforcement learning (DRL) algorithm, to create a low-complexity and adaptive framework for simultaneous transmit beamforming and RIS phase shift design. We formulate the joint optimization problem as a Markov decision process (MDP), where an agent learns a continuous policy to map the observed channel state directly to beamforming vectors and phase shifts to maximize the SE. Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed method performs close to the conventional alternating optimization approach, while significantly reducing the online execution time.

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